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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, I.

by S. Söderhjelm

1. Introduction

The observation schemes and data reductions for HIPPARCOS are optimized for "single" stars (photocentric motion less than 1 mas). A sizeable proportion of the objects observed will be more complicated, however, (cf. NDAC/LO/039), and special methods have to be developed for their proper reduction. The present series of papers aims to provide (by extensive numerical experiments) the guidelines for constructing this reduction software.

This first paper describes simulations for wide (2-36") double stars with only rectilinear motions (long period binaries and optical doubles). The main purpose is to ascertain if there are combinations of separation and magnitude difference (e.g. 5"+5" $\Delta m < \text{sep} < 25''$ as proposed by Lindegren and Kovalevsky) that should be excluded from the Input Catalogue on these grounds only.

2. Overview of the present simulation programs

A program-package has been developed that simulates in detail the frame by frame observations of a specified binary. The output from these simulations are preprocessed Fourier-coefficients, which are then fitted by iterative LS to a model binary. The binary parameters given by the solution are then compared with the true ones, and the differences may be related to the many (instrumental and stellar) variable input parameters.

The first part (SCAN) simulates the scanning motion of the satellite and gives as output a list of transit times across a "reference" position on the sky. Most of the subsequent runs are for the "typical" position $\alpha = 0^h$, $\delta = 35.26^\circ$ ($\beta = 32.0^\circ$). At this position there are 20 groups with 147 individual FOV-passages in a 2½ year interval.

The second module (SAMP) simulates the individual photon counts for a specified binary at the reference position, and performs also the preprocessing in order to compress the data to manageable size. This

simulation needs detailed specification of the instrument parameters (grid distortion, OTF-model, IFOV-profile), as given in Section 3.

The solution program (BISOL) is an iterative LS-scheme where twelve binary parameters (one magnitude and five astrometric parameters per star) are improved using the preprocessed "observations" from SAMP. When the positional parameters of the binary are known within a few tenths of an arcsec (as is probably true for most wide systems), the solution often converges within about five iterations.

3. Details for SCAN and SAMP

To simulate the scanning motion of the satellite, the nominal attitude is used as a basis. Each time a nominal FOV crosses the reference position, the heliographic angles and their derivatives are given realistic (gaussian) deviations from their nominal values. A new crossing time is calculated with the deviations taken into account, and times and angles are output for use by SAMP. So far, all experiments have been made with standard deviations 200 arcsec in the angles (ν , ξ , Ω), $0.8 \text{ arcsec s}^{-1}$ in the angular rates ($\dot{\nu}$, $\dot{\xi}$, $\dot{\Omega}$) and $0.002 \text{ arcsec s}^{-2}$ in the spin acceleration $\ddot{\Omega}$.

In SAMP, the position of each component star is given relative to the reference position, and with the attitude specified by SCAN, the field-coordinates (w, z) are calculated rigorously for the beginning and end of each frame. (At other times, they are linearly interpolated). The field coordinates are transformed to grid-coordinates G by the relation

$$G = 170749.01 w + 59.6 z + 1850 w^2 + 610 wz - 1100 z^2 + \\ + (0.0024 + 0.0012 f - 0.024 zf) C \quad (1)$$

where f is the field index (± 1), and C the star colour (B-V-0.5).

The IDT observations are made by a moving IFOV, and a simple gaussian model is developed for the pointing errors. First, the IFOV aiming point is defined. For close pairs, this may be the photocentre, but for separations above some $10''$, the two components should be centered alternately (see Section 4). In any case, we have first the *à priori* (catalogue error) uncertainty, constant for all observations of the object. The standard deviation is usually taken as $\sigma_c = 1 \text{ arcsec}$. Then we assume a gaussian deviation constant over each field crossing (standard deviation σ_F , typically 1.5 arcsec), and a smaller one at each new IFOV positioning (standard deviation $\sigma_s = 0.2 \text{ arcsec}$). In reality, each gaussian deviation is

applied independently in the two coordinates.

The IFOV sensitivity profile is approximated by the following relations, giving maximum relative error ($\Delta f/f$) 4% relative to the data in Matra doc. E26-HIP-09497

$$\begin{aligned} f(r) &= \exp [-0.4124(r/23'')^2 - 1.4201(r/23'')^3] & r < 15'' \\ f(r) &= \exp [-1.4189 + 4.5562(r/23'') - 5.0192(r/23'')^2] & 15'' < r < 30'' \\ f(r) &= \exp [24.5543 - 48.0166(r/23'') + 26.5464(r/23'')^2 - \\ & \quad - 5.0025(r/23'')^3] & 30'' < r < 50'' \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

An important effect besides this intensity attenuation is the phase shifts introduced in the outer parts of the IFOV profile. Calculations by Lindegren (letter to E. Zeis 1984-12-19) gives the following typical (?) values (radians) for the shifts in the first and second harmonic of the IDT signal

$$\begin{aligned} d_1 &= 4.6 \cdot 10^{-5} (\Delta w/1'')^3 [1 + (r/23'')^6]^{-1} & (3) \\ d_2 &= 0.6 d_1 \end{aligned}$$

with Δw the part of the depointing along the scanning direction.

A star of V-magnitude V (colour $C = B - V - 0.5$) is assumed to give a "nominal" count rate

$$I_0 = 6.41 \cdot 10^6 [1.1 - 2700(w^2 + z^2)] 10^{-0.4H} \quad (4)$$

where the HIPPARCOS-magnitude is given by

$$H = V + 0.158 + 0.25 C - 0.13 C^2 \quad (5)$$

As observed behind the grid, with IFOV depointing r , the effective IDT count rate is given by the OTF-model

$$\begin{aligned} I &= B + f(r) I_0 [1 + M_1 \cos(2\pi G + d_1) + M_2 \cos(4\pi G - v_2 + d_2) + \\ & \quad + M_3 \cos(6\pi G - v_3)] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where d_1 and d_2 are the phase errors given by (3), and v_2, v_3 are field- and colour-dependent phase errors given by

$$\begin{aligned} v_2 &= (-1.71 + 1.38 C) \text{ wf} \\ v_3 &= (1.06 + 1.37 C) \text{ wf} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The modulation coefficients are taken to be

$$\begin{aligned} M_1 &= 0.727 - 0.057 C - 0.4 wf - 25 w^2 \\ M_2 &= 0.262 - 0.023 C - 0.3 wf - 20 w^2 \\ M_3 &= 0.006 - 0.003 C \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

and the background B is fixed at 72 Hz.

The IDT-intensities (6) for the two components are calculated at each required sampling interval (1/1200 s), and their sum is discretized into an "observed" integer count by a Poisson routine. The counts from each frame (and each of one or two nominal IFOV pointings) and their corresponding reference phases ($p = 2\pi G_{\text{ref}}$) are then transferred to a standard pre-processing routine (45 phase bins, cf. NDAC/LO/061). The output is the five Fourier coefficients b_i (together with their mean errors) giving the "best" approximation

$$\text{count} \approx b_1 + b_2 \cos(p) + b_3 \sin(p) + b_4 \cos(2p) + b_5 \sin(2p) \quad (9)$$

These framewise sets of Fourier coefficients are the "observations" to be fitted in BISOL.

In order to set up a linearized model (see Section 5), the derivatives of the grid-coordinates with respect to the astrometric parameters are needed. These are calculated (once per frame) in SAMP as

$$\frac{\partial G}{\partial a} = \frac{\partial G}{\partial w} \frac{\partial w}{\partial a} + \frac{\partial G}{\partial z} \frac{\partial z}{\partial a} \quad (10)$$

where a stands for any astrometric parameter. Here $\partial w/\partial a$ and $\partial z/\partial a$ follow from the attitudes and positions, while $\partial G/\partial w$ and $\partial G/\partial z$ are found by differentiating (1). (The error in a grid-coordinate calculated by the differential coefficients (10) may be about 0.5 mas at 30 arcsec from the reference position).

In typical runs (147 frames, 512 samples per frame), the SAMP-routine needs about 1 hour CPU-time on the HP 9000 at Lund Observatory.

4. The binary generation and observing strategy

The magnitudes and colours of the two component stars are input, together with their separation. A model binary (random position angle) is then generated, with the photocentre at the reference position, and with proper motions and parallax that may or may not be equal for the two components.

These "true" astrometric data (in a rectangular xy-system centered on the reference position) are then input to SAMP.

Depending on the IFOV aiming point, three different "pointing strategies" (P1-P3) may be selected. For P1, the aiming point is the photocentre of the binary, for P2 it is the brighter component. In both cases, the same aiming is used throughout, and only one set of Fourier coefficients is calculated in each frame. In aiming P3, the two components are centered alternately in the IFOV, and we have thus two pointings and two sets of Fourier coefficients per frame.

It remains to specify the observation times allotted. The standard observing strategy with 16 cycles of 20 slots in each frame is followed. The IFOV is fixed during each slot, but 8 IDT-samples are obtained. All runs in the present series use slots 1-4, which means calculating 512 samples per frame in SAMP. In strategy P3, the slots might be divided unequally between the pointings, but so far the "symmetric" scheme (slots 1-2 for the primary, slots 3-4 for the secondary pointing) has been used.

5. The solution program

The BINARY SOLUTION program adjusts the parameters of a binary to fit the Fourier b-coefficients from SAMP. The basis for this adjustment is an "ideal" OTF-model with no phase errors and with $M_3 \equiv 0$. In this case, the IDT counts for a multiple star will be

$$I = B + \sum_{k=1}^n \left[I_k \cdot 1 + M_1 \cos[2\pi(G_k - G_{\text{ref}} + G_{\text{ref}})] + M_2 \cos[4\pi(G_k - G_{\text{ref}} + G_{\text{ref}})] \right] \quad (11)$$

and the Fourier coefficients relative to G_{ref} are then

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 &= \sum_{k=1}^n I_k + B \\ b_2 &= M_1 \sum_{k=1}^n I_k \cos[2\pi(G_k - G_{\text{ref}})] \\ b_3 &= -M_1 \sum_{k=1}^n I_k \sin[2\pi(G_k - G_{\text{ref}})] \\ b_4 &= M_2 \sum_{k=1}^n I_k \cos[4\pi(G_k - G_{\text{ref}})] \\ b_5 &= -M_2 \sum_{k=1}^n I_k \sin[4\pi(G_k - G_{\text{ref}})] \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

These expressions are equally valid for any number (n) of components, but at present n = 2. The intensities I_k are "effective" ones, including the IFOV sensitivity.

The basic twelve variables adjusted are

x_1	H-magnitude for the primary component
x_2-x_6	astrometric parameters for the primary
x_7	magnitude difference (secondary minus primary)
x_8-x_{12}	relative astrometric parameters (sec - pr)

The reason for using relative coordinates is that one may then obtain the constrained solution $x_{10} = x_{11} = x_{12} = 0$ (common parallax and proper motions) by simply deleting three variables in the normal equations. With pointing strategy P3 we introduce also x_{13} , the mean IFOV attenuation (mag) for one star when the other is observed. (Some runs were made with two individual attenuation parameters. This produced no gain in accuracy, but gave instead some extra problems for systems with large magnitude difference).

Linearized observation equations are now derived from (12), using the derivatives relative to the astrometric parameters $\partial G/\partial a_j$ from SAMP. As an example, for b_2 , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial b_2}{\partial x_1} &= -c_m M_1 (I_1 \cos p_1 + I_2 \cos p_2) \\ \frac{\partial b_2}{\partial x_{j+1}} &= -2\pi M_1 (I_1 \sin p_1 + I_2 \sin p_2) \frac{\partial G}{\partial a_j} \quad j=1,5 \\ \frac{\partial b_2}{\partial x_7} &= -c_m M_1 I_2 \cos p_2 \\ \frac{\partial b_2}{\partial x_{j+7}} &= -2\pi M_1 I_2 \sin p_2 \frac{\partial G}{\partial a_j} \quad j=1,5 \\ \frac{\partial b_2}{\partial x_{13}} &= \frac{\partial b_2}{\partial x_7} \quad (\text{pointing at primary}) \\ \frac{\partial b_2}{\partial x_{13}} &= \frac{\partial b_2}{\partial x_1} - \frac{\partial b_2}{\partial x_7} \quad (\text{pointing at secondary}) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Here p_k are the phases $2\pi(G_k - G_{\text{ref}})$ calculated by the differential expressions

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_1 &= 2\pi \sum_{j=1}^5 \frac{\partial G}{\partial a_j} x_{j+1} \\
 p_2 - p_1 &= 2\pi \sum_{j=1}^5 \frac{\partial G}{\partial a_j} x_{j+7}
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

and c_m stands for $0.4 \ln 10$. Similar sets are easily derived for the other b_i 's.

For each frame, five (or ten) observation equations are thus formed, with the rhs equal to the observed (from SAMP) minus the computed (from eqs 12) b_i . Originally, the equations were weighted in the standard way by division by the estimated mean errors of the b_i (from SAMP). This works well for pointing strategies P1 and P2, but gives problems in P3 when the fainter star is centered. The primary may then fall on the steep "edge" of the IFOV, and even small pointing errors will give large variations in I_1 that may "drown" the meaningful signal. This is a main reason for the difficulties at around 20" separation, but a simple weight-adjustment has been found to help considerably.

The formal b_i -error for each frame is simply increased by an empirical factor (derived in SAMP) that takes the pointing-error contribution into account. This factor may also be derived theoretically, and it has the approximate form

$$\text{m.e(actual)/m.e(formal)} \sim \left[1 + C \int_1^0 \frac{\left| \frac{df(r)}{dr} \right|^2}{f(r)} \sigma_F^2 \right]^{1/2} \tag{15}$$

where $f(r)$ is the IFOV profile, and C a constant different for the different b_i 's. The function $\left| \frac{df(r)}{dr} \right|^2 / f(r)$ has a broad (FWHM=14") peak around 20", and even after the weight-corrections, the solutions are less accurate in this region of separations.

The program has to be started with astrometric parameters reasonably close to the true ones in order to avoid slit ambiguities. For wide (well-known) doubles, this will be no problem. After all observation equations have been accumulated, the (12 x 13 or 13 x 14) set of normal equations is solved, giving the requisite corrections to the x_j 's. With these improved parameters, the observation equations are formed anew, and the solution is repeated. The iterations are terminated when all corrections are less than a small fraction ϵ of their mean errors. (In practice, this ϵ is allowed to increase with increasing numbers of iterations, but mostly $\epsilon = 0.01$ and convergence occurs in about five iterations = 5 min

CPU-time on the HP9000).

When the solution has converged, the relative astrometric parameters are transformed back to give data for the secondary and primary separately. These final values (with estimated mean errors) may now be compared with the true binary parameters, and such comparisons are the main output of the present simulations. All runs have been made in two "modes". In the "free" solution, all twelve (or thirteen) parameters are estimated, that is, there is no assumption about any physical connection between the stars. In the "fixed" mode, the parallax and proper motions are constrained to be equal for the two components, as expected for a physical binary of long period.

As an interesting illustration of the importance of choosing the right parameters, I may mention some experiments where the "modified" Fourier q-parameters were used. These are defined by

$$\text{IDT count} \approx q_1 + q_2 \cos(p + q_3) + q_4 \cos(2p + 2q_5) \quad (16)$$

and one version of SAMP produced q_1 - q_5 instead of b_1 - b_5 . A BISOL with the corresponding observation equations did produce correct solutions (with identical estimated mean astrometric errors), but only in 2-3 times as many iterations.

6. The standard runs

As illustrative examples, five "series" of runs have been made, with separations 2-36 arcsec in each series. The stellar data are given in Table 1, thus there is always one component with $V=8.5$. The idea is to see how the errors for this "standard" component varies as the companion varies from 3 magnitudes fainter to 3 magnitudes brighter. In each series, 2x18 different binaries have been generated, with separations 2, 4 ..., 36 arcseconds. The IFOV pointing strategy P3 was used throughout (as it is inseparable from P1 at small separations), and also the standard values $\sigma_c = 1''.0$, $\sigma_F = 1''.5$, $\sigma_s = 0''.2$.

Table 1. Stellar data for the standard series.

Ser.	V(pr)	B-V(pr)	V(sec)	B-V(sec)
A	8.50	0.50	11.50	1.00
B	8.50	0.50	10.00	0.75
C	8.50	0.50	8.50	0.50
D	7.00	0.25	8.50	0.50
E	5.50	0.00	8.50	0.50

One problem is how to characterize the astrometric errors by a single quantity for each run. There are many measures that may be used, but I have adopted simply the rms deviation in the five astrometric parameters, equalizing e.g. a 3.5 mas position error with a 3.5 mas/y proper motion error. This unsophisticated measure shows rather large statistical variations, but it is easy to interpret and suffices well for the present exploratory study. Table 2 shows such rms-values for ranges of 6" in separation (2 x 3 runs, 30 individual astrometric parameter values).

Table 2. Rms deviations (mas) in the astrometric parameters for the 8^m.5-component in each of the standard series. Subscript 1 stands for the "free" solutions, subscript 2 for the "fixed" ones. Each value is calculated from 5 x 6 astrometric O-C:s.

Sep (")	A ₁	A ₂	B ₁	B ₂	C ₁	C ₂	D ₁	D ₂	E ₁	E ₂
1 - 7	1.0	1.0	1.1	0.8	1.2	0.7	2.3	1.6	19	10
7 - 13	1.3	1.4	1.2	1.2	1.5	1.2	3.0	1.8	12	7.2
13 - 19	2.1	2.1	1.6	1.6	1.8	1.7	3.8	3.1	19	9.0
19 - 25	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.2	3.2	1.3	11	4.0
25 - 31	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.6	1.0	0.6	4.2	2.0
31 - 37	0.6	0.6	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.7	1.0	0.7	1.2	0.6

The data in Table 2 gives a lot of information about the double star observation capabilities of HIPPARCOS. In all series, there is an error increase in the "middle" ranges of separation, in rough conformity with the related expression (15). The rapid deterioration for the secondary when the primary is more than about a magnitude brighter is also apparent. Again, eq. (15) gives an indication of the cause: the IFOV "edge-effect" is worse for brighter primaries.

To test this rather heuristic reasoning, alterate runs were made for series A, C and E with σ_F increased to 2.5 (which may also be closer to the expected value). One would expect now a larger error-increase in Ser. E than in Ser. A, and as seen in Table 3, this is approximately true. The mean increase for 7-25" separation is about 40 % in Ser. E, 30 % in Ser. C, but rather a decrease in Ser. A.

Table 3. Rms deviations (mas) analogous to those in Table 2, but with $\sigma_F = 2.5$ instead of 1.5.

Sep (")	A ₁	A ₂	C ₁	C ₂	E ₁	E ₂
1 - 7	1.0	0.8	0.8	0.7	11	6.4
7 - 13	1.0	1.0	1.6	1.4	12	8.5
13 - 19	1.7	1.6	2.7	2.3	23	11
19 - 25	1.3	1.3	2.0	1.5	18	10
25 - 31	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.8	5.6	2.1
31 - 37	1.1	1.1	1.0	0.7	1.7	1.1

The other large error-contribution factor is the IDT phase error in eq. (3). In this case, the effect may be proportional to $f(r) d_1(r)$, which interestingly has a very similar dependence on the separation as eq. (15). A new set of alternative A, C, E-runs was made with zero phase errors (d_1). The results in Table 4 show now a larger decrease in Ser. A (40 %), and smaller ones in Ser. C (20 %) and E (10 %).

Table 4. Rms deviations (mas) analogous to those in Table 2, but with zero IDT phase errors.

Sep(")	A ₁	A ₂	C ₁	C ₂	E ₁	E ₂
1 - 7	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.7	13	8.5
7 - 13	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.7	12	6.7
13 - 19	1.0	0.8	1.5	1.3	13	6.9
19 - 25	1.1	1.1	1.3	1.2	16	9.0
25 - 31	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.6	4.5	2.1
31 - 37	1.0	0.9	1.0	0.7	1.2	0.8

From the data in Tables 2 - 4 one may now rather safely estimate the errors for realistic combinations of σ_F and d_1 . For Ser. A - C (observation of the primary component), the astrometric errors are seldom more than doubled as compared with the single star case. (The single star error for an 8.5 magnitude star with 2 slots observing time is about 1.0 mas, in good agreement with the binary data for large separations.)

7. The observing strategy

The runs described in Section 6 were all made with IFOV pointing strategy P3 (alternate pointings at the two components). An obvious question concerns the limit separation where this starts to be more effective than a fixed pointing at the photocentre. Again, only series A, C, E were repeated, this time with pointing strategy P1. Table 5 gives sample rms-values, in some cases from a rather limited number of experiments.

Table 5. Rms deviations (mas) for photocentric (P1) vs. individual (P3) IFOV-pointing.

Sep(")	A ₁ (P1)	A ₁ (P3)	C ₁ (P1)	C ₁ (P3)	E ₁ (P3)	E ₁ (P3)
1 - 7	0.9	1.0	1.3	1.2	12	19
7 - 13	0.8	1.3	1.4	1.5	19	12
13 - 19	0.6	2.1	1.6	1.8	59	19
19 - 25	-	1.2	3.2	1.4	-	11
25 - 31	-	0.9	5.6	0.9	-	4.2

In Ser. C, the P1-values grow definitely larger only for separations above some 20 arcsec. In Ser. A, the P1-values are smaller than the standard P3-ones, because we are studying the primary, and the secondary disturbs less as it gets closer to the IFOV edge. Conversely, when we study the secondary in Ser. E, the values deteriorate faster. In all cases, Separations as small as 10 arcsec may be equally well observed with a single (P1) as with two (P3) IFOV pointings.

A second question is about the separation limit above which an "uninteresting" companion star may be neglected. For this purpose, the "standard" series were again run, but now with pointing strategy P2 (pointing at the 8^m.5 star). As can be seen from the data in Table 6, a secondary 3 magnitudes fainter than its primary (Ser. A) may be neglected at all separations. For the other series, the separation limit grows with the brightness of the neglected component. Roughly, we may estimate it at 25" for $\Delta m = 1.5$, 30" at $\Delta m = 0$, 40" at $\Delta m = -1.5$ and 60" at $\Delta m = -3$.

Table 6. Rms deviations (mas) for 4 slots on 8^m.5-component (P2) vs. 2+2 slots on the two components alternately (P3).

Sep(")	A ₁ (P2)	A ₁ (P3)	B ₁ (P2)	B ₁ (P3)	C ₁ (P2)	C ₁ (P3)	D ₁ (P2)	D ₁ (P3)	E ₁ (P2)	E ₁ (P3)
13 - 19	0.7	2.1	4.2	1.6	-	1.8	-	3.8	-	19
19 - 25	1.0	1.2	1.6	1.1	5.0	1.4	-	3.2	-	11
25 - 31	0.8	0.9	0.6	0.8	1.5	0.9	7.7	1.0	31	4.2
31 - 37	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.9	0.6	0.8	1.6	1.0	4.8	1.2
37 - 43	-	-	-	-	0.8	-	1.1	-	4.4	-
43 - 49	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.7	-	3.0	-

As a simplified rule, we may say that above 30 arcsec separation, an "uninteresting" secondary is better left unobserved. The same applies for a secondary more than (say) 2.5 magnitudes fainter than the program star. A brighter companion to a program star is probably already observed, but in some special cases, it may be necessary to ascertain this.

8. Untested variations

For lack of time, there are many other variations that have not been tried. The following list gives some obvious examples:

1. The random deviations in the scan-law are of fixed magnitude. Probably, this is not very important.
2. A single reference position on the sky has been used throughout. From a few early experiments at high and low ecliptic latitude, the interesting variations seem to be rather independent of the reference position.

3. The star colours do change the OTF (cf. eqs. 6-8). No systematic investigations of these effects has been made, but in the standard series, unequal magnitude stars have been given unequal colours.
4. The a priori IFOV pointing error (σ_c) has been fixed at 1".0, which should not be too far from the truth. The "slot" pointing error σ_s has been set at 0".2, and probably the "total" $(\sigma_s^2 + \sigma_p^2)^{1/2}$ is the important variable.
5. The weighting might be improved, at least other schemes should be tested.

9. Conclusions

It has been show by extensive numerical experiments (more than 400 CPU-hours on the HP 9000 at Lund Observatory) that the problems for HIPPARCOS in relation to wide double stars are less than anticipated. Interesting data may be obtained for any wide double, even in the previously "forbidden" range of separations ($5'' + 5'' \Delta m < \text{sep} < 25''$). There is a loss of accuracy at about 10-25" separation, depending mostly on the IFOV pointing error (σ_p) and the IDT phase errors (d_1), but the errors are large mostly for the faint component in a pair.

These results allow us to formulate the following simple rules for double star inclusion in the Input Catalogue:

1. Double stars with separation less than 10 arcsec may be observed as single objects (IFOV pointing at photocentre).
2. Doubles with separation 10 - 30 arcsec should be observed as two separate objects, with the observing time equally divided between them.
3. Program stars attended by "uninteresting" secondaries that are either more than 30 arcsec distant or more than 2.5 magnitudes fainter are best observed as single stars (secondary neglected).

In subsequent papers, some of the "variations" listed in Section 8 may be studied further, and also of course the complications with more than two components, orbital motion and so on. Hopefully, however, the above recommendations should not need to be revised.